

energy costs and CO2 impact of PV-facades

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background

- BIPV as a additional potential to use renewable energy for the energy turnaround.
- Evaluating the energy potential

assessment criteria

simulation

parameters:

calculated lifetime estimation:	30 years
Interest rate:	3%
Maintenance costs	3 ct/kWh
horizontal global irradiation Zurich (CH):	1127 kWh/m ² year
system efficiency/performance ratio:	0.82
PV cell technology:	c-Si
CO ₂ emissions 2016:	1'839 kg/kWp (bauteilkatalog.ch)
CO ₂ emissions 2040:	800 kg/kWp (REAL scenario, BfE)
pv-specific system costs 2016:	3'000 CHF/kWp
pv-specific system costs 2025:	2'250 CHF/kWp

irradiation

Irradiation on facades:

global irradiation on facades subject to azimuth orientation

irradiation

Irradiation on facades:

economical:

Production costs of PV-facades in several orientations in comparison to the energy scale from the local energy supplier

Azimut of facade(0°=South, -90°=East, +90°West, 180=North)

CO2 impact:

CO2-Impact of PV-facades in several orientations in comparison to the swiss energy mix

conclusion

conclusion:

- the CO₂ amortisation of different BIPB orientations depends on the yearly irradiation sum on the plane (location & shading).
- The comparison of the CO₂ impact of the local energy mix is significant for the assessment of BIPV orientations.

outlook:

- The CO₂ impact of the energy mix improved with the increasing annex of renewable energy in the electric supply.
- Technological progress in production efficiency and energy output will increase the CO₂ impact of PV.

Thank you

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